

TECHNOLOGICAL APPROACH TO THE DEVELOPMENT OF COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE IN TEMURBEKLAR SCHOOL STUDENTS

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Abstract. The article shows the effectiveness of the use of pedagogical and information technologies in the development of communicative competence in the students of "Temurbek School". In particular, the issues of developing communicative competence through the use of technologies such as designing, brainstorming, and clustering in the process of learning English are revealed.

Keywords. competence, communicative competence, communication, technological approach, design, brainstorming, cluster, interactive methods, communicative skills.

Аннотация. В статье показана эффективность использования педагогических и информационных технологий в развитии коммуникативной компетентности у учащихся «Школы Темурбек». В частности, раскрываются вопросы развития коммуникативной компетенции посредством использования таких технологий, как проектирование, мозговой штурм, кластеризация в процессе изучения английского языка.

Ключевые слова. компетентность, коммуникативная компетентность, коммуникация, технологический подход, проектирование, мозговой штурм, кластер, интерактивные методы, коммуникативные навыки.

Creative methods of education (brainstorming, speech on a socially important topic) are aimed at creating creative products of subjective and objective significance, distinguished by novelty and originality. Their advantage lies in constantly mobilizing students' mental energy and increasing their interest in learning, in the presence of constant interaction between the teacher and students and their interactions with each other.

These teaching methods focus on the development of intellectual, linguistic, behavioral skills and abilities, increase the motivation and emotionality of perceiving the studied material, processing and mastering it.

The design method (research projects, defense of presentations) is a method that includes the process of forming students' communicative competence in the English language class through independent research and cognitive activity to solve a problem that can be theoretical and practical. The teacher organizes the

creative, independent work of schoolchildren, as a rule, only indicates the purpose of the work without indicating what and how to do it.

The design method has the highest level of problem solving and cognitive independence of students, it is an effective means of forming communicative competence and developing creative activity. For example, as part of our practical work, students are invited to prepare a lecture on a relevant topic and discuss it with the audience: "Mode und Konsum in der modernen Gesellschaft", "Globale Wirtschaft: Probleme und Perspektiven", etc. [4].

We are sure that the formation of communicative competence of students N.V. Uvarina defines it as "a complex of creative abilities that manifests and develops in production activities, as well as a complex of mental neoplasms of a person that is formed during his maturity" [2]. V.G. Rindak and A.V. According to Moskvina, "the effectiveness of a person's activity is clearly determined by his creative potential, as an integral part that reflects the need, readiness and opportunities for creative self-awareness and self-development; defines a person's attitude to creativity; shows the ability to create new things both in the world around him and in himself; provides effective interaction and operational efficiency" [1].

Thus, interactive teaching methods help to solve several problems at the same time in the formation of communicative competence of students in the process of teaching English: they help to establish emotional connections between students, and teach teamwork; develop the ability to form one's own point of view and defend one's thoughts and positions, listen to the interlocutor's opinion, tolerance, use the rules of speech etiquette to solve communication problems.

Due to the active use of interactive methods of teaching in the process of forming students' communicative competence in English classes, it is possible to achieve effective results in the development of students' communicative competence necessary for the life of modern society.

Summarizing the above, we came to the conclusion that in the process of teaching English to schoolchildren, the formation of not only the set of knowledge, skills and abilities, but also communicative competence is of primary importance.

The most effective task of students' formation of communicative competence is achieved through the use of interactive teaching methods in organizing the process of formation of communicative competence in teaching English to students, which is characterized by a wide palette of possibilities. and

contributes to the formation of their most important communication skills and abilities.

Factors such as insufficient formation of communication skills among Temurbek school students: formation of opinions suitable for different communication situations; low level of understanding of speech in English; insufficient development of the problem of communicative competence development required the optimization of didactic conditions aimed at the formation of communicative competence in the process of teaching English [5].

In the current conditions of changing the main directions of the student's personality development, the task is to form not only an intellectual person, but also a person who is ready for intercultural communication. In the conditions of linguistic globalization, qualitative changes are taking place in the social order of the society in order to form a well-rounded person capable of active communication.

In the modern conditions of teaching English, methods of education based on a student-oriented approach occupy a leading position, their criteria are expressed in interactive forms and methods of teaching. Their use allows to fully realize the main goals of teaching English.

According to many scientists, in order to achieve the results of the metasubject, it is necessary to rely on the formation of basic competence, which ensures active activity in various spheres of society.

Communicative competence is one of the main competences in the 3-level competence hierarchy system, along with general subject and subject. We believe that the didactic tools of the subject "English" are the most convenient for the formation of communicative competence due to their flexibility.

The development of communicative competence, including the ability to interact with others, the ability to perform various social roles, means the meta-subject results of mastering a certain amount of knowledge in English at the basic school.

Today, the educational system is focused on innovative and effective activities. This requires the search for new forms of education, the use of non-traditional types and methods of teaching, and the creation of didactic conditions in line with the times. Communication-oriented education is one of the few educational activities that meet all these requirements.

Until recently, the main goal of school education was the formation of skills, but now a new type of person with 5 competencies is required:

- social tolerance;

- communicative - informational;
- competence, which makes it possible to realize the desire to learn throughout life [3].

The subject "English language" includes the following content areas:

1. Communication skills on the main types of speech activity.
2. Language tools and their management skills.
3. Socio-cultural knowledge and skills. All of them are interrelated, and the absence of any of them destroys the unity of the science of "English language". Therefore, it is necessary to take a comprehensive approach to the organization of the English language teaching process.

Pedagogical conditions of the English language teaching process for students of Temurbek school should help to expand students' worldview, form communication skills, increase creative and cognitive activity, independence.

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